

Semantic Structures of Balinese Verb “Bring”: Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach

Eka Dwi Putra ¹, I Wayan Simpen ², I Nengah Sudipa ³, I Nyoman Sedeng ⁴,

Article history:

Received: July 30, 2023; Accepted: September 18, 2023; Displayed online: September 30, 2023; Published: September 30, 2023

Keywords

*Natural semantic
metalanguage;*

Balinese;

semantic primes;

BRING;

polysemy;

Abstract

This article analyzed words in Balinese that share the same semantic prime: *BRING* using Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM). The Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) is a linguistic theory that reduces lexicons down to a set of semantic primitives. This research was conducted using the descriptive qualitative approach. The data that were found in this research were the words that are connected to the semantic prime *BRING* in the Balinese language. The aim of this research is to explain (1) as a basis for analysis lingual especially in analyzing semantic structure of verbs. (2) Adding to the treasures of semantic knowledge, especially the original meaning of the verb "Bring" in Balinese. (3) Raising elements of lexical semantics, especially elements of original meaning and polysemy. The data were collected using interview guidelines, recording equipment, and writing equipment. An interactive model of data analysis is used to analyze the data. From the data that were collected and analyzed, there are 14 words that are connected to semantic prime *BRING*, namely: *ngaba / makta, nyuwun, mundut, negen, nyelet, ngandong, ngenyang, nyangkil, nyangkol, nampa, nenteng, ngangkut, ngandeng and maid* ". These words are similar but not exactly synonymous and they will create misconception in diction.

¹ Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia.

² Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia.

³ Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia.

⁴ Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Denpasar, Indonesia.

1. Introduction

Balinese is a regional language that is very rich in vocabulary. Apart from that, Balinese has its own letters with a number of vowels and consonants along with punctuation marks in them. In its use as a communication tool by Balinese speakers, there are levels according to the social position of the speaker, this social position includes caste, age, position in society, both in government and traditional positions in Balinese society. Apart from that, the Balinese language has many verbs that can be reviewed from the perspective of Natural Semantic Metalanguage. This article reviews one form of the verb "bring" in Balinese using the Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) approach. Explanation of the meaning of "bringing" in Balinese, as a medium for writers to deepen some Semantic concepts, especially Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM).

Semantic studies based on the theory of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) have been carried out on many languages in the world, such as Leo (Thailand), Mangaaba-Mbula, Malaysia (Austronesian), Mandarin Chinese, Polish, Spanish, Hawaiian Creole English, Acehnese, Japanese and several indigenous Aboriginal languages in Australia, such as Bunuba, Yankunytjajara (Goddard, 2002: 12). Research on the Balinese language from the perspective of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) has also been widely carried out. Sudipa (2004) has studied the verbs "take" and "tie" in Balinese from the perspective of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM). Suastini (2014) has studied the verb "see" in Balinese from the perspective of natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM), Widani (2016) has also studied the verb "take" in Balinese from the perspective of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM). Parwati (2018) studied the verb "to cook" in Balinese from the perspective of Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM)

In this paper the author is interested in analyzing the verb "bring" because this object is very interesting to research in semantic studies, where the Balinese verb "bring" has a complex physical activity that includes prototypical motivation, the entity being treated, the tools used, how to bring. The verb "bring" has special semantic features called subtle differences (Goddard, 2002) which are inherent in several lexicons. Example: The meaning of "bring" (Indonesian) can be expressed by several lexicons in Balinese. These lexicons have formed configurations of meaning that differentiate between one lexicon and another, especially lexicons that are in the same field of meaning. Other meanings that have the same field of meaning as the verb "bring" in Balinese are *"ngaba/makta, nyuwun, mundut, negen, nyelet, ngandong, ngenyang, nyangkil/nyingal, nampa, nenteng, ngangkut, gandeng and maid"*.

Verb Concept

Verbs or verbs (Latin: *verbum*, "word") are a class of words that express an action, existence, experience, or other dynamic meaning. This type of word generally becomes a predicate in a phrase or sentence. Based on the object, verbs can be divided into two: Transitive verbs: verbs that require a complement or object, such as hitting (a ball), and intransitive verbs: verbs that do not require a complement, such as running.

Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) Concept

Original meaning is a set of meanings that cannot change because humans inherit them from birth (Goddard, 1996: 2; Mulyadi, 1998: 35). This original meaning can be explained as a reflection of the very basic human mind. The original meaning can be replicated from natural language which is the only way to represent meaning (Wierzbicka 1996:31). The explication of meaning must include the

*Semantic Structures of Balinese Verb "Bring": Natural Semantic Metalanguage Approach
(Eka Dwi Putra, I Wayan Simpen, I Nengah Sudipa, I Nyoman Sedeng)*

meaning of words that are intuitively related or at least have the same field of meaning, and the meaning of these words is analyzed based on their components. A set of original meanings is expected to explain complex meanings into simpler ones without having to go around in circles, as stated by Wierzbicka, (1996:12) and Goddard, (1996:2): "It is impossible to define all words. In defining we employ a definition to express the idea which we want to join to the defined words, and if we then wanted to define "the definition" still other words would be needed, and so on to infinity".

Weirzbicka (1996), said 'NSM theory combines the philosophical and logical tradition in the study meaning with a typological approach to the study of language, and with broadly based empirical cross-linguistic investigations. Goddard (2010:459) The Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) is a decompositional system of meaning representation based on empirically established universal semantic primes, i.e., simple indefinable meanings which appear to be present as word meanings in all languages. She further discussed that The Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) is a mini-language which corresponds to the shared core of all languages. It has as many versions as there are languages in the world; for example, there is an English NSM, a Polish NSM, an Indonesian NSM, and so on. But all these different versions match. (Weirzbicka, 16 Nov.2020 sharing session)

The analysis applies two approaches at once, (i) mapping the meaning with configuration based upon the *entity, process, instrument* and *result* and (ii) Explication using 65 semantic primes as the following table

Category	Semantic Primes
1. Substantives	I, YOU, SOMEONE, PEOPLE, SOMETHING/THING, BODY
2. Relational Substantives	KIND, PART
3. Determiners	THIS, THE SAME, OTHER~ELSE~ANOTHER
4. Quantifiers	ONE, TWO, SOME, ALL, MUCH/MANY, LITTLE/FEW
5. Evaluators	GOOD, BAD
6. Descriptors	BIG, SMALL
7. Mental predicates	THINK, KNOW, WANT, DON'T WANT, FEEL, SEE, HEAR
8. Speech	SAY, WORDS, TRUE
9. Actions, Events, Movement, Contact	DO, HAPPEN, MOVE, TOUCH,
10. Existence, Possession	BE (SOMEWHERE), THERE IS, BE (SOMEONE/SOMETHING), (IS) MINE
11. Life and Death	LIVE, DIE
12. Time	WHEN/TIME, NOW, BEFORE, AFTER, A LONG TIME, A SHORT TIME, FOR SOME TIME, MOMENT
13. Space	WHERE/PLACE, HERE, ABOVE, BELOW, FAR, NEAR, SIDE, INSIDE, TOUCH (CONTACT)
14. Logical Concepts	NOT, MAYBE, CAN, BECAUSE, IF
15. Intensifier, Augmentor	VERY, MORE
16. Similarity	LIKE/AS/WAY

(Source: Goddard & Weirzbicka, 2014)

Non-compositional Polysemy Concept

Polysemy is a single lexicon form that can express two different original meanings (in Sudipa, 2012: 54). In this case, there is no compositional relationship between one exponent and another because the exponents have different grammatical frameworks. In the action verb to bring, there is an incompositional action between doing and moving, so that the experience has the following exponent: "X does something to Y and because of this Y moves to part of X at the same time X and Y move to a new place. X does something like this.

According to Wierzbicka (1996:35) and Beratha (2000:208) Paraphrasing must follow the following rules.

1. The paraphrase must use a combination of a number of original meanings proposed by Wierzbicka. A combination of a number of original meanings is required in connection with the claims of the NSM theory, namely that a form cannot be expressed using only one original meaning.
2. Paraphrasing can also be used using elements that are unique to a language. This can be done by combining elements that are unique
3. Language itself to decipher meaning.
4. Paraphrased sentences must follow the syntactic rules of the language used to paraphrase.
5. Paraphrase always uses simple language.
6. Paraphrased sentences sometimes require special indentation and spacing

2. Materials and Methods

There was written data was collected by observation and note-taking (Cargil, et.al.2013). The collected data was furthermore analyzed by applying Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM). The method used in this research is a descriptive-qualitative method by following the following steps: data classification, analyzing the semantic structure of the verb "bring", and describing the components obtained to produce a meaning configuration regarding special features, especially applying paraphrasing.

3. Results and Discussions

In every language, including Balinese, verbs are divided into three types, namely (a) Circumstance verbs; (b) Process verbs and (c) Action verbs. The focus of the following study refers to one type of action verb, namely carrying, with polysemy: doing and moving. The combination of doing and moving reveals a relatively high Undergoer influence because the verb class includes prototypical transitive verbs. Prototype transitive verbs have a subject as the agent and a direct object as the patient (Wierzbicka, 1996:421).

In Balinese, for example, the verb "bring" is classified as a type of doing which has polysemy with moving. A study using NSM analysis of the verb variant "bring" will show the structure: If the person "brings" then the component mapping "X does something to Y" and because of this "Y moves to X". At the same time X and Y move places, X wants this. X does something like this. The lexicon of "bring" is based on the tool used, the movement model, and the part of the entity that is treated by the agent. The variant meanings of the verb "bring" can be the same as the meanings: "*ngaba/makta, nyuwun, mundut, negen, nyelet, ngandong, ngenyang, nyangkil/nyingal, nampa, nenteng, ngangkut, ngandeng and maid*".

3.1 Ngaba or makta 'bring'

Ngaba used on people of ordinary social status in Bali

Example:

- a) *I bapa luas ke carik ngaba arit miwah tambah.*
Father go to ricefield *bring* sickle and hoe
'Father went to the rice fields *brought* a sickle and hoe'
- b) *Yen cening masekolah ingetan ngaba buku miwah potlote.*
If child go to school remember *bring* book and pencil
'If you want to go to school, remember to *bring* books and pencils'

Makta means "bring". Balinese is used to speak to interlocutors who have a higher social status (caste, social status in traditional communities/government).

Example:

- a) *Ratu Suryan titiang, titiang tangkil puniki makta jinah hasil laba duene.*
Queen my I come this *bring* money profit results yours
'My Queen, I have come to *bring* your profits'
- b) *Pak Gede, sampunan meweh-meweh makta barang-barang akeh sekadiniki.*
Mr. Gede not bother bother *bring* stuff lot of like this
'Mr. Gede, don't bother *bringing* a lot of stuff like this'

In the sentence above, the verb *ngaba/ makta* has a general meaning of "bring", it can be used in various situations. These words are used to carry something (object). The media commonly used are hands and other tools. The exponents and sub-exponents of the verb "*ngaba/makta*" can be explicated through the following paraphrase:

Explication:

- At that time, X did something to Y
- X does something (without or with tools)
- Because of this, Y moves to X
- At the same time X and Y move to a new place
- X wants this
- X does something like this

3.2 Nyuwun 'bring'

Nyuwun is bringing an item or object using the agent's head and hands as a means of supporting the weight of the item or object.

Example:

- a) *I meme nyuwun baas a kampil.*
Mother bring rice art sack
'Mother brought a sack of rice'

Explication:

- At that time, X did something to Y.
- X did something with his own head as a load-bearing device
- Because of this, Y moves to X
- At the same time X and Y move to a new place
- X wants this
- X does something like this

3.3 Mundut “bring”

Mundut is bringing something that is highly respected, such as someone who has a high social position or something related to community beliefs/traditions, such as *sesuhunan; pratima, galuh, rencang, statues of the god Vishnu, Ratu Ngurah (Barong) and Ratu Istri (Rangda)*. This process is carried out by the agent using his shoulders or head with his hands as a tool to support the weight.

Example:

- a) *Jero mangku Dalem mundut sesuhunan Ratu Istri (Rangda)*
Temple-priest Dalem bring sesuhunan Ratu Istri (Rangda)
 Dalem temple-priest brings Sesuhunan Ratu Istri (Rangda)

The explication of the verb "mundut" can be explicated through the following paraphrase:

At that time, X did something to Y (Y was something that was highly respected)
 X does something to Y with his head or shoulders
 Because of this, Y moves to X
 At the same time X and Y move to a new place
 X wants this
 X does something like this

3.4 Negen “bring”

Negen is bringing an item using the agent's shoulders and hands as a means of supporting the load, either using additional equipment in the form of a *sanan* "straight bamboo or wooden stick that is slightly elastic" or without additional equipment.

Example:

- a) *I bapa negen tambah ke carik.*
 Father *bring* hoe prep ricefield
 "Father *brought* a hoe to the ricefield"

Explication:

At that time, X did something to Y
 X did something with the shoulders without or using additional tools
 Because of this, Y moves to X
 At the same time X and Y move to a new place
 X wants this
 X does something like this

3.5 Nyelet “bring”

Nyelet is bringing something or object that is small/flat/thin by tucking it at the waist (between the waist and the belt or waist strap being worn). This something or object is usually a sharp object such as: a sickle, a knife.

Example:

- a) *Pan Made nyelet tiyuk di bangkiangne lantas ia melaib ngalih I Kobar.*
 Person *bring* knife prep waist then pron run look pron person
 "Pak Made brought a knife in his waist and then ran to look for I Kobar."

Explication:

At that time, X did something to Y,
 X did something by slipping into the waist

Y is a small, flat, thin, and sharp object.
Because of this, Y moves to X
At the same time, X and Y move to a new place
X wants this
X does something like this

3.6 Ngandong "bring"

Ngandong is bringing something or someone using the back and hands as a tool to support the weight.

Example:

- a) *I buta ngandong I Lumpuh mejalan ngiterin desa dadi gegendong.*
Pron blind *bring* Pron paralyzed walk around village be beggar
The Blind man carried the Crippled man around the village as a beggar.

Explication:

At that time, X did something to Y
X did something to his back himself with the help of his hands.
Because of this, Y moves to X
At the same time X and Y move to a new place
X wants this
X does something like this

3.7 Nyangkil "bring"

Nyangkil is bringing an object or person using the waist and hands as a tool to support the weight of the object or person.

Example:

- a) *Men Brayut nyangkil pianakne luas ke peken.*
Person *bring* child-Poss go prep market
Mom Brayut brought her child to the market"
- b) *I dadong nyangkil nyuh a bungkul uli tukade.*
Grandmother *bring* coconut art one from river
Grandmother brought a coconut from the river.

The explication of the verb *nyangkil* is as follows:

At that time, X did something to Y
hands to support the load
Because of this, Y moves to X
At the same time X and Y move to a new place
X wants this
X does something like this.

3.8 Ngenyang "bring"

Ngenyang is bringing someone (children) using the waist and hands to support the person's weight.

Example:

-
- a) *Putri ngenyang adine sambilange nyampat.*
 Person bring brother-Poss whilst sweep
 Putri brings her brother while sweeping."

The exponents and subexponents of the verb *ngenyang* can be explicated through the following paraphrase:

At that time, X did something to Y. Y was a toddler
 X does something with his waist and hands to support the weight
 Because of this, Y moves to X
 At the same time X and Y move to a new place
 X wants this
 X does something like this.

3.9 *Nyangkol* "Bring"

Nyangkol is bringing someone or an object using the agent's stomach and hands to support the weight of the person or object.

Example:

- a) *Dugas linuhe ibi sanje I bapa sepananan nyangkol Ayu tur melaib pesu.*
 Time earthquake yesterday evening father hurry bring Person ran exit
 During the earthquake yesterday evening, father hurriedly brought Ayu out of the house."

The exponents and sub exponents of the verb *nyangkol* can be explicated through the following paraphrase:

At that time, X did something to Y
 his hands to support the load. Because of this, Y moves to X
 At the same time X and Y move to a new place
 X wants this
 X does something like this

3.10 *Nampa* "bring"

Nampa is bringing an item or object using the agent's palm which is positioned parallel to the shoulder to support the load. The item or object being carried usually has a flat side.

Example:

- a) *Dagange ento ngindeng nampa kapar misi buah-buahan.*
 Seller that around bring tray with fruits
 The seller went around bringing a tray of fruit

Explication:

At that time, X did something to Y
 X did something with the palm of the hand which is placed at shoulder level
 Because of this, Y moves to X
 At the same time, X and Y move to a new place
 X wants this
 X does something like this

3.11 Nenteng “bring”

Nenteng is bringing something or an object that has a small part where the fingers hold the load. Example:

- a) *I Kaki nenteng nyuh uli tegale.*
Grandfather *bring* coconut from farm-Poss
Grandfather brought coconuts from the garden.

The exponents and subexponents of the verb *nenteng* can be explicated through the following paraphrase:

- At that time, X did something to Y.
X did something with his fingers.
Because of this, Y moved to X
At the same time, X and Y move to a new place
X wants this
X does something like this

3.12 Ngangkut “bring”

Ngangkut is bringing an object or a person/human using a means of transportation (two-wheeled, four-wheeled, truck, bus, etc.).

Example:

- a) *Bise ngangkut muride melali ke Bedugul.*
Bus-Poss *bring* student picnic prep Place
The bus brought the students on an picnic to Bedugul.

Explication:

- At that time, X does something to Y
At the same time X and Y move to a new place
X wants this
X does something like this

3.13 Ngandeng “bring”

Ngandeng is bringing person or object/goods using two-wheeled means of transport (bicycle, motorbike).

Example:

- a) *Galih ngandeng Ratna aji sepeda kretrek.*
Person *bring* Person with bicycle old
Galih gave Ratna a ride on an old bicycle.

The exponents and sub-exponents of the verb "*ngandeng*" can be explicated through the following paraphrase:

- At that time, X did something to Y
X did something with the conveyance two wheels
Because of this, Y moves to X
At the same time, X and Y move to a new place

X wants this
X does something like this

3.14 *Maid* “bring”

Maid means bringing a person or goods with or without using tools that can be pulled by hand. The burden of the person or object being carried is not on the agent (it is supported by the ground, floor, etc.).

Example:

a) *I Wayan maid adine aji dokar-dokaran.*
 Person bring brother-Poss with toy
 I Wayan brought his younger brother with dokar-dokaran toy.

Explication:

At that time, X does something to Y.
 X does something with or without tools.
 Y burden does not fall on X
 Because of this, Y moves to X
 At the same time X and Y move to a new place
 X wants this
 X does something like this

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis using paraphrase/explication analysis techniques, mapping with natural language in the form of canonical sentences, with supporting data for the Balinese verb *ngaba* ‘bring’ can be analyzed thoroughly based on the **Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM)** theory. This study has provided a fairly clear picture of the explication technique which states one form or lexicon for one meaning and one meaning for one form or lexicon. The semantic structure of the Balinese verb “*ngaba*” can be expressed in several lexicons, namely: *ngaba/makta, nyuwun, mundut, negen, nyelet, ngandong, ngenyang, nyangkil, nyangkol, nampa, nenteng, ngangkut, ngandeng* and *maid*.”

Acknowledgements

The current work is self-funding research. The author delivers his gratitudes to the editor of Growingscholar publisher for publishing this research.

References

- Allan, Keith, 2001. *Natural Language Semantics*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Cross Linguistic Syntax from Semantic Point of View (NSM Approach) 1-5 Australia.
- Goddard, Cliff. 1996. *Semantic Theory and Semantic Universal* (Cliff Goddard Con-ensor)
- Kesuma, Tri Mastoyo Jati. 2010. "Verba Transitif dan Objek dapat Lesap dalam Bahasa Indonesia".
Linguistik Indonesia, Jurnal Ilmiah MLI. Jakarta: Unika Atmajaya.
- Kridalaksana, Harimukti. 2008. *Kamus Linguistik*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- Mulyadi, 1998. *Struktur Semantis Verba Bahasa Indonesia*. Tesis S2, Linguistik Denpasar.
- Sudipa, I Nengah. 2004. *Verba Bahasa Bali, sebuah Kajian Metabahasa Semantik Alami*. Disertasi
Doktor Linguistik-Denpasar.
- Sudipa, I Nengah 2011. *Semantik Konsep Dan Aplikasi Natural Semantik Metalanguage (NSM)*.
Denpasar: Program Pasca-sarjana Universitas Udayana.
- Sudipa, I Nengah 2012. *Makna "Mengikat" Bahasa Bali: Pendekatan Metabahasa Semantik Alami* 49-
68. Denpasar: Jurnal Kajian Bali
- Sutjiati-Beratha, NI, 1997. *Basic Concepts of a Universal Semantic Metalanguage* *Linguistika* 110-115.
Denpasar: Program Magister Linguistik UNUD.
- Wierzbicka, Anna. 1996. *Semantics: Prime and Universal*. Oxford: Oxford University.